

Growth strategy and aggressive strategy

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Abstract

This article tries to distinguish between growth strategy and aggressive strategy as one of the implications of a strategy that should be chosen (according to the strategic position – relative) of an organization based on the results of identification and evaluation of the internal environment and external environment (business and macro environment) in applying strategy management (strategy formulation, strategy implementation, and strategy evaluation) using SWOT analysis tools - Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Treats. In simple terms, of course, the explanation is inseparable from the conceptual and practical approach, nor is it inseparable from the relative approach of an organization in implementing these two strategies.

Keywords: Growth strategy; Aggressive strategy

Concept and Difference – Practice

A growth strategy is a competitive strategy to develop a company (according to the size of the company), the goal is to create a competitive advantage (Weinzimmer et al., 2023), strategically and with long-term goals. Growth strategies offer several strategic options comprehensively (Rodrik, 2005), ranging from internal growth strategies (conservative) to external growth strategies according to the potential implications of managerial success and potential risks, that can be implemented in practice (i.e. the basis of the relative strategic position – the identified internal & external environment). Also inseparable from the growth patterns adopted, for example for generic growth of high-tech new businesses, organic growth, partnership growth, and acquisition growth (Zou et al., 2010), to sharpen competitive advantage, of course, this is not regardless of the type, size, scale and age of the company (Alaaraj et al., 2018), it has one business unit but has differentiated products, or the company has several business units with its product line (Amrouche & Yan, 2015).

Strategy aggressiveness, is the trend to engage in a variety of sustainable, diverse, or unique actions to challenge competitors and improve their relative competitive position (Hughes-Morgan et al., 2018). Aggressive strategies are more directed at behavior and actions that demonstrate a responsive attitude in responding to market changes (Stępień & Weber, 2019) rather than passive or adaptive, including the intensity of managerial attitudes in implementing one or several types of growth strategies by allocating more resources, because they are aggressive/responsive and can even directly engage/deal with competitors (Weinzimmer et al., 2023), the goal is similar to creating a competitive advantage, for example: an instantaneous aggressive strategy with advertising investments that erode competitor sales (Amrouche & Yan,

2015), including an effort to increase growth/anticipate strategies-overcome competitor attacks/environmental turbulence & market/macro changes (sudden/long-term implications) (Kriemadis et al., 2021; Kozubíková et al., 2017).

Conclusion

Growth strategy is a type of comprehensive strategy/process ranging from internal growth strategy (conservative) to external growth strategy, which is chosen to be implemented as a competitive strategy to develop the strategy, the types of strategies are slow or fast according to the implications of the chosen strategy and the level of risk. Aggressive strategy is part of the model and way of implementing a strategy that reflects the attitude, reaction and action of management that is more offensive/open in developing one strategy or several strategies, including in implementing among several types of selected growth strategies as a form of anticipation of the strategy considered the most appropriate (relative management/company) to be developed. The goal is similar to create a competitive advantage/long-term goal. Explicitly, aggressively more closely with the immediate anticipation of strategies to overcome competitor attacks/market changes/macro changes or even sudden, to accelerate growth (it can be involving, attacking/directly confronting competitors). In the growth strategy there is an approach called the internal (conservative) growth strategy, which indicates at first not directly confront with competitors although in the end it is possible that there will be an excess impact on the behavior & actions of competitors, which also ultimately requires anticipating strategies to overcome and deal with them in an effort to maintain and increase sustainable competitiveness.

Even in the business landscape in today's digital era, the development of digital technology in the disruptive era of 21st century technology is increasingly challenging the concept and practice of strategic management, because the business environment is becoming more dynamic, consumption behavior patterns and consumer tastes are changing rapidly. The culture of click-and-click in a connected, interactive and participatory digital ecosystem in the customer/producer community through websites, digital platforms (social media), and other sophisticated communication tools, online marketing - e-commerce and the adoption of digital platform-based marketplaces are increasingly affecting marketing managerial and the implications of formulating - implementing strategies that are more in line with the business landscape of the modern era, are also inseparable because consumers and society today more educated.

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